

Vitamin D acts synergistically with PI3K inhibitors in animal model of asthma

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Abstract

Phosphoinositide 3-kinase (PI3K) plays a pivotal role in the recruitment and activation of certain inflammatory cells in asthma and vitamin D significantly inhibits various inflammatory cells in asthma. Therefore, we aim to investigate the role of PI3K inhibitor; wortmannin and vitamin D alone and combinations of together in allergic Ovalbumin (OVA) animal model of asthma. Wistar albino rats were sensitized with OVA and, upon OVA challenge, developed airway eosinophilia and neutrophilia. Administration of dexamethasone, vitamin D, wortmannin, combination of dexamethasone+vitamin D, vitamin D+wortmannin and dexamethasone+vitamin D+wortmannin significantly ($P<0.05$) attenuated OVA-induced eosinophils and neutrophils but we did not find any effects on monocytes, lymphocytes and total cells counts. The results of present study, indicated that vitamin D acts as synergistically with PI3K inhibitors and play significant role in chronic asthma.

Keywords: Asthma, vitamin D, PI3K inhibitors

Introduction

Asthma is an inflammatory condition that has been validated in clinical settings. Corticosteroids, a unique class of anti-inflammatory medications, play a crucial role in controlling asthma symptoms (1). The prevalence of asthma is currently increasing; more than 300 million individuals are affected worldwide (2). Most types of asthma can be controlled; however the disease has not been eradicated using the currently available therapies. The adverse effects of corticosteroid therapy, the occurrence of drug resistance, the recurrence of asthma attacks, and the cost of asthma treatment are among the highly problematic issues currently faced by clinicians (2).

PI3K family plays an important role in inflammatory lung diseases particularly asthma. PI3K control inflammatory cells growth, differentiation, survival, migration, proliferation, and mediator production (3-5). Termination of PI3K signalling can be mediated phosphatase and tensin homolog deleted on chromosome 10 protein (PTEN) (6). It was reported that the PTEN knockout mice is embryonically lethal and PTEN plays a pivotal role in Th2-mediated airway inflammation and airway responsiveness (7). In addition, PTEN over expression

reduced airway hyperresponsiveness and vascular endothelial growth factor expression in a murine model of asthma (8). Vitamin D is a hormone that can be obtained from the diet or produced endogenously by a series of reactions that culminate in the most active metabolite of vitamin D, $1\alpha,25(\text{OH})_2\text{-vitamin D}_3$ ($1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$). Classical actions of $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ are mediated through the vitamin D receptor (VDR) which is a member of a superfamily of nuclear steroid hormone receptors. Upon $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ binding VDR translocates to the nucleus, dimerizes with retinoid X receptor (RXR) and modulates the expression of target genes. Although a number of $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ responsive genes are known, the exact mechanism of growth regulation by $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ is not completely defined; however, an increase in p21 and/or p27 is an almost universal feature (9).

One of the central contributing factors which facilitates the asthma is attributed to the phosphoinositol-3 kinase PI3K-AKT pathway. In asthma, activation of AKT occurs most frequently due to the loss of tumor suppressor phosphatase and a tensin homologue deleted in chromosome 10 (*PTEN*). Loss of *PTEN* and activation of AKT has been shown to downregulate the expression of p21 and p27 by a number of mechanisms (10-14) and $1,25(\text{OH})_2\text{D}_3$ involve in upregulation of p21 and/or p27 (9) while activation of PI3K/AKT downregulates their expression (10-14). We hypothesized that pharmacological inhibitors of PI3K will cooperate with the antiasthmatic action of vitamin D.

Materials and Methods

Animal husbandry and feeds

Wistar albino rats (200-250 g) of either sex were housed in a room maintained at $22 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ with a relative humidity of $55 \pm 5\%$ and a 12 h light-dark cycle. Animals had free access to standard pellet diet (certified

Amrut brand rodent feed, Pranav Agro Industries, Pune, India) and filtered tap water. All experiments were carried out with strict adherence to ethical guidelines and were conducted as per protocol approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) and as per Indian norms laid down by the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA), New Delhi. Throughout the entire study period, the animals were monitored for growth, health status, and food intake capacity to be certain that they were healthy.

Sensitization and Challenge with OVA and Treatment

Animals were divided into nine groups ($n=6/\text{group}$). Group I, non-sensitized controls, received distilled water (2.5 ml/kg); group II, the model control group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received distilled water (2.5 ml/kg); group III, the reference standard group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received Dexamethasone (Dexa) (2.5 mg/kg); group IV, the experimental group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received vitamin D (50 IU/kg), group V, the experimental group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received combination of vitamin D (50 IU/kg) and Dexa (2.5 mg/kg); group VI, the experimental group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received wortmannin (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), group VII, the experimental group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received combination of wortmannin (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) and vitamin D (50 IU/kg), group VIII, the experimental group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received combination of wortmannin (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) and Dexa (2.5 mg/kg) and group IX, the experimental group, was ovalbumin sensitized and then received combination of wortmannin (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), Dexa (2.5 mg/kg) and vitamin D (50 IU/kg). These rats were sensitized with 100 μg ovalbumin (adsorbed in 100 mg/ml of aluminum hydroxide in saline) by i.p. injection on days 0 and 14 (general sensitization) in all rats. Rats were anesthetized before being challenged with

100 µg of OVA in 100 µl of saline; intranasally for 3 days. On days 21–23, for group II to IX daily doses of drug or vehicle by i.p. injection 1 h prior to OVA administration. The wortmannin were dissolved in DMSO (0.4 mg/ml) and diluted with 0.9% NaCl was administered systemically (i.p.) twice to each animal: once on day 21 (1 h before the first airway challenge with OVA) and the second time on day 23 (3 h after the last airway challenge with OVA as described previously by Tigani et al., (15) and Pinho et al., (16).

Results

Effect of treatments on eosinophils

The eosinophils count in blood samples recovered from the model control animals were markedly increased ($p < 0.05$) compared to the non-sensitized controls. However, the numbers of circulating eosinophils ($p < 0.05$) in the blood were significantly decreased in dexamethasone, vitamin D, wortmannin ($p < 0.05$), combination of vitamin D-dexamethasone, combination of wortmannin-vitamin D, combination of wortmannin-dexamethasone and combination of wortmannin-vitamin D-dexamethasone treated animals, respectively, compared to those numbers seen in the ovalbumin sensitized rats (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Effect of treatments on eosinophils. Values shown are the mean±S.E.M. (n=6). [@] $p < 0.05$

compared to the non-sensitized control. ^{*} $p < 0.05$, compared to the OVA (ovalbumin)-sensitized vehicle-treated model control, [#] $p < 0.05$ compared to the dexamethasone treated, ^{\$} $p < 0.05$ compared to the wortmannin, ⁺ $p < 0.05$ compared to the combination of wortmannin, vitamin D and dexamethasone. S= Ovalbumin sensitized, VitD= Vitamin D, Dexa=Dexamethasone, Wort=Wortmannin.

Effect of treatments on neutrophil.

The neutrophils count in blood samples recovered from the model control animals were markedly increased ($p < 0.05$) compared to the non-sensitized controls. However, the numbers of circulating eosinophils ($p < 0.05$) in the blood were significantly decreased in dexamethasone, vitamin D, wortmannin ($p < 0.05$), combination of vitamin D-dexamethasone, combination of wortmannin-vitamin D, combination of wortmannin-dexamethasone and combination of wortmannin-vitamin D-dexamethasone treated animals, respectively, compared to those numbers seen in the ovalbumin sensitized rats (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Effect of treatments on neutrophil. Values shown are the mean±S.E.M. (n=6). [@] $p < 0.05$ compared to the non-sensitized control. ^{*} $p < 0.05$, compared to the OVA (ovalbumin)-sensitized vehicle-treated model control, [#] $p < 0.05$ compared to the dexamethasone treated, ^{\$} $p < 0.05$ compared to the wortmannin, ⁺ $p < 0.05$ compared to the combination of wortmannin, vitamin D and dexamethasone. S= Ovalbumin sensitized, VitD= Vitamin D, Dexa=Dexamethasone, Wort=Wortmannin.

Effect of treatments on monocytes

We did not find any significant changes in the neutrophils count in blood samples recovered from the model control animals and treatment groups (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Effect of treatments on monocytes. Values shown are the mean±S.E.M. (n=6). S= Ovalbumin sensitized, VitD= Vitamin D, Dexa=Dexamethasone, Wort=Wortmannin.

Effect of treatments on lymphocytes

We did not find any significant changes in the lymphocytes count in blood samples recovered from the model control animals and treatment groups (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Effect of treatments on lymphocytes. Values shown are the mean±S.E.M. (n=6). S= Ovalbumin sensitized, VitD= Vitamin D, Dexa=Dexamethasone, Wort=Wortmannin.

Effect of treatments on Total cell

We did not find any significant changes in the total cell count in blood samples

recovered from the model control animals and treatment groups (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Effect of treatments on total cell. Values shown are the mean±S.E.M. (n=6). S= Ovalbumin sensitized, VitD= Vitamin D, Dexa=Dexamethasone, Wort=Wortmannin.

Discussion

In this study we showed that pi3k inhibitors in combination with vitamin D synergistically inhibit the inflammatory cells in asthma. Vitamin D used as a single agent has been shown to possess antiasthmatic qualities in a number of animal models. In this light, synergism between vitamin D, corticosteroid and pi3k inhibitors suggests that more therapeutic efficacy can be achieved by combining these agents in asthma and potentially reducing systemic toxicities and side effects of corticosteroids.

Bronchial asthma is an inflammatory disease of the airways characterized by airway obstruction and increased airway responsiveness. Eosinophils play important roles in the pathophysiology of asthma (17). Many inflammatory mediators attract and activate eosinophils via signal transduction pathways involving the enzyme PI3K and found there is a potential correlation between asthma and Phosphatidylinositol 3 kinase (PI3K) signaling pathway (15, 18-21) (3-7). In this study we found that PI3K

activity increased significantly after allergen challenge in a murine model of asthma. Administration of wortmannin a potent PI3K inhibitors, reduced eosinophilic and neutrophilic inflammation. Our data are consistent with the results obtained in a study reported by Tigani et al. (15) showing that wortmannin inhibits the increased number of eosinophils and eosinophil OVA-challenged animals. Palframan et al. (20) reported that wortmannin inhibited IL-5-induced selective release of eosinophils from perfused bone marrow, as well as selective eosinophil chemokinesis in vitro. The use of PI3K inhibitors has revealed the involvement of PI3K in the transduction of activation signals generated by many inflammatory mediators in eosinophils and play an important role in the induction and maintenance of asthma.

PTEN is one of the most frequently mutated tumor suppressors in human cancer. It is also essential for embryonic development, cell migration, and apoptosis (22,23,24). PTEN has been implicated in regulating cell survival signaling through the PI3K/Akt pathway (22, 25,26,27). Several reports have shown that PI3K inhibitors are potent inhibitors of eosinophil degranulation (18-21). Wortmannin, a PI3K inhibitor, potently inhibits peroxidase release from eosinophils (20) and blocks neuropeptide-induced chemotaxis and IL-5-induced β 2-integrin-dependent adhesion to ICAM-1-coated surfaces in human eosinophils (18,19). Moreover, Ni et. al., (28) demonstrated that treatment of mice with dexamethasone resulted in the restoration of PTEN expression. In vitro studies using human lung epithelial cell A549 revealed that dexamethasone was able to increase both PTEN promoter activity and gene expression which suggest that the effect of glucocorticoids on asthma may partly pass through the PTEN signaling pathway, and that PTEN is a new target gene involved in the response to dexamethasone (28). Previous report has shown that vitamin D inhibits pi3k signalling pathway (29, 30).

Moreover, VDR acted as a transcription factor of PTEN and induces the expression of PTEN (31). Therefore, vitamin D which blocks the action of PI3K, might reduce eosinophilic inflammation.

Conclusion

The results show that the synergistic interaction between vitamin D and PI3K inhibitor, and they can effectively reduce airway inflammation induced by inhaling OVA in bronchial asthma rats by inhibiting PI3K signaling pathway.

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